

The National Services Network EURAXESS As an Efficient Tool For Integration In the European Research Area

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Abstract. EURAXESS is a unique initiative of the European Commission, which aims to promote the growth of research careers and stimulate the researcher's mobility in European area. The initiative was created to protect and develop the European space of research and to help the scientific community to improve the career and social development.

Keywords: EURAXESS, European Commission initiative, researcher's mobility, European Research and Innovation areal, career, social development.

Portal Național informațional EURAXESS – aparat efficient pentru integrarea în spațiu de cercetare Europeană

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Rezumat. EURAXESS este o inițiativă unică, lansată de Comisia Europeană pentru promovarea carierei de cercetare și facilitarea mobilității cercetătorilor în spațiul European. Inițiativa a fost creată pentru a stimula, proteja și dezvolta spațiul european de cercetare și inovare, oferind comunității de cercetare accesul la îmbunătățirea carierei și dezvoltarea socială.

Cuvinte-cheie: EURAXESS, inițiativa Comisiei Europene, mobilității cercetătorilor, spațiul european de cercetare și inovare, carieră, dezvoltarea socială.

Национальный информационный портал EURAXESS как эффективный инструмент для интеграции в Европейское исследовательское пространство

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Аннотация. EURAXESS является уникальной инициативой Европейской Комиссии, которая направлена на содействие роста научно-исследовательских карьеры и стимулирует мобильности исследователей в Европе. Инициатива была создана чтобы защищать и развивать европейское пространство исследований и инноваций и помогать научному сообществу в улучшение карьеры и в социальном развитии.

Ключевые слова: EURAXESS, инициатива Европейской Комиссии, мобильности исследователей, Европейское пространство исследований и инноваций, карьера, социальное развитие.

Введение

The European Research Area, in which national science is becoming increasingly present, is by definition an open space where scientific knowledge, technology, and researchers are moving freely. This is why the EURAXESS initiative aims to promote career opportunities and the mobility of European researchers. Currently, forty European states are involved in the EURAXESS network, which acts at European, regional, and national levels. Through EURAXESS, researchers receive information about all aspects regarding the mobility, both online as well as through personal consultants at

their respective research facilities. A Pan-European jobs database helps candidates to find vacant posts at research institutes and organizations that promise equitable work recruitment and growth opportunities for the researchers. EURAXESS is based on four pylons:

EURAXESS Jobs – a free recruitment tool by which researchers can find up-to-date information about vacant positions, financing opportunities, and grants from all Europe. Of crucial importance is the posting of one's CV on this platform, thus permitting a feedback from potential employers. On the other hand, companies and research institutes are given

the possibility to freely post vacant jobs announcements and to search for valued international researchers. Users can also access national EURAXESS portals of partner countries that contain information regarding jobs, financing opportunities, and personalized services from each country.

EURAXESS Services – a network comprising over two hundred Service Centers from 40 European countries. With a team of well-informed personnel, these centers help researchers (and their families, every time this is the case) to plan and organize their moving to a foreign country. This personalized assistance is helping researchers to be less stressed about accommodation, visas, work permits, etc.

EURAXESS Rights is offering all the information regarding the *European Charter of Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers*, fundamental documents functioning as guides for good practices, created in order to promote equal rights and obligations for all European researchers, specifying their role, responsibilities, ad rights, but also that of the financers/employers. Thus, attractive research careers, a better employment rate and work conditions for European researchers are assured. The guidelines of the Charter and the Code are equally addressing European research organizations, and public or private universities. The Science Academy of Moldova (SAM), and through it the national science community, adopted the European Charter of Researchers and Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers in December 2011, agreeing to apply their principles in the field of science and innovation in the Republic of Moldova.

EURAXESS Links – a network established between the USA, Japan, China, Singapore, and India, addressing European researchers working outside the European Research Area. It offers detailed information about research in Europe, European research policies, job opportunities in Europe, international cooperation and transnational mobility. The platform also offers networking web-instruments for researchers.

Our country acceded to the EURAXESS initiative in October 3rd, 2011, when the Center for International Projects of the SAM was designated as host and liaison institution for the EURAXESS Services Network in the Republic of Moldova. The first step for implementing the principles of the EURAXESS mechanism in our country consisted in creating the special portal (www.euraxess.md) for promotion of the initiative, resting on three pylons: EURAXESS Services, EURAXESS Rights, and EURAXESS Links. This was followed by the creation of a national network of local contact points, meant to support the personnel of each one's institution by directly assisting researchers returning to or leaving the institution (presently, the network comprises 25 people). However, a limitation of the local contact points is that they cannot provide services for researchers from other institutions. That is the reason why three national regional EURAXESS centers have been established (Center, South, and North). Another goal of the EURAXESS initiative at national level was to encourage Moldovan research institutes to subscribe to the standards of the Human Resources Strategy for Researchers (HRS4R), a tool that helps employers and financers form the field of research to apply the principles of the Charter and the Code, resulting in receiving the logo "Excellence in Research", thus increasing the international visibility and prestige of the respective institutions. Until now, three institutions from our country received the HRS4R logo: The University of the Science Academy of Moldova, the State University of Moldova, and the National Institute for Economic Research.

Furthermore, the EURAXESS National Service played a major role in organizing science promotion activities across the country, including both editions of the European Researchers' Night (2013 and 2015). Additionally, with direct help from the EURAXESS National Services Network, local public interested in research and creativity experienced an unusual form of dissemination of scientific ideas, called

“Science Slam”: a form of scientific communication, originating in Germany, gaining popularity around the world by presenting research in a fun, creative, and easy-to-understand manner, therefore “opposed” to classic forms such as conferences or congresses. Recently, Science Slam Moldova reached its 4th edition, increasing its audience and, implicitly, its popularity with each edition.

A major milestone in the recognition of the importance, efficiency, and success of the National Services Network was the inclusion of our country in the “EURAXESS – on tour” program, comprising 34 cities from 16 European countries, including Belgium, Switzerland, France, Montenegro, Portugal,

Romania, etc., which reached Chişinău at November 5, 2015, supplying young researchers with information about the necessary steps for the integration in the research and innovation environment provided by the European Research Area.

For more information about EURAXESS and the EURAXESS National Services Network: Dorina Harea, Local Contact Point, Center for International Projects of the SAM, Tel.: +373-22-27-20-24, E-mail: dorina.harea@euraxess.md, 1 Ştefan cel Mare Blvd., office 513, Chişinău, Republic of Moldova.

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